

Modeling Synthetic Spectra of Thermonuclear (Type Ia) Supernovae

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BACHELOR THESIS

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Abstract

In astrophysics Type Ia supernovae are of great importance. They are used as distance indicators for cosmology and they contribute to the chemical evolution of galaxies. Despite of their remarkable importance several of their properties are not yet fully understood, including their progenitor stars and the explosion mechanism. Different approaches have been used to overcome this lack of knowledge. In this work we describe a "backward modelling" approach named the "Abundance Tomography Method" (ATM). This method makes use of spectral features of the explosions to determine the chemical composition of the ejecta. Here, this ATM is carried out by means of the radiative transfer Monte Carlo code TARDIS. We describe and explain how one can run TARDIS and present a simple example of a synthetic spectrum, consistent with observed data. Moreover, we present an abundance stratification profile of a subluminous Type Ia supernova which was obtained by using this code and which differs from that of normal ones.

Contents

1	Introduction	7
2	Objectives	11
3	Methodology	13
3.1	Radiative Transfer	13
3.2	Monte Carlo Radiative Transfer Methods and TARDIS	15
3.2.1	Random Sampling	15
3.2.2	The Radiative Transfer code TARDIS	16
3.2.3	Discretization and Initialization	16
3.2.4	Monte Carlo packet propagation	17
3.2.5	Spectral Synthesis	18
3.3	Application of TARDIS	19
3.3.1	Running TARDIS	19
3.3.2	Example TARDIS Calculation	19
3.3.3	Backwards Modelling with TARDIS	20
4	Conclusion and Outlook	22

1 Introduction

The uniformity of the light curves of Supernovae Type Ia (SNe Ia) gives to these objects the potential to be used as cosmic distance indicators ("standardisable candles") (Phillips 1993). Therefore SNe Ia are also a main tool to measure the cosmologic expansion rate (Hamuy et al. 1995; Tripp 1998) directly related with the discovery of the accelerated expansion of the Universe (Riess et al. 1998; Perlmutter et al. 1999) with the possible explanation of a "dark energy" dominated universe (Turner & Tyson 1999). They are also important for the chemical evolution of galaxies (Kobayashi et al. 1998) and may regulate galaxy formation (Efstathiou 2000). Although SNe Ia are used in many ways, they are still under study due to aspects related to their unknown progenitors and uncertainties in the explosion mechanism.

Figure 1.1: Classification scheme of supernovae. Taken from Turatto (2003)

The classification of supernovae is mainly based on their spectra, more exactly on their emission near maximum light. The basic concept to characterize the two main types is the presence or absence of hydrogen in the spectra. SNe Ia show no evidence of hydrogen, while Type II do. The main key to allocate the different subclasses of Type I supernovae is the existence of strong Si II absorption lines, while Type Ib and Ic do not present this features, but He I lines instead. In particular, Type Ia exhibit a strong Si II line at around 6150 Å (Harkness & Wheeler 1990) (see Fig. 1.1).

SNe Ia are very luminous and bright and at maximum light they can outshine their host galaxy. Near maximum light their spectra are characterized by broad P Cygni profiles, characteristic for expanding atmospheres, not only of Si II but also of Ca II, S II, and O I lines of neutral and singly ionized elements (see also Fig. 1.2) (Branch & Tammann 1992), developing blends of P Cygni permitted Fe II lines shortly thereafter. At later stages they develop blends of non permitted emission lines of ionized iron and cobalt (Branch 1998).

Figure 1.2: Early-time spectra of three different SNe Ia at approximately 1 week past B-band maximum. SN 1990N in NGC 4639, SN 1987N in NGC 7606 and SN 1987D in MCG+00-32-01 (taken from Filippenko (1997))

Identifying the progenitors of SNe Ia is crucial in many aspects: galaxy evolution in terms of the ejected material, the explosion mechanism, and the determination of the key cosmological parameters, among others (Livio 2000). The general belief is that SNe Ia are thermonuclear disruptions of mass-accreting white dwarfs. The composition of these white dwarfs is commonly assumed to be carbon-oxygen (C-O), although oxygen-neon-magnesium (O-Ne-Mg) and helium white dwarfs are unlikely but not excluded (Branch et al. 1995).

In general terms two scenarios for the progenitor systems of SNe Ia have been suggested: the single-degenerate (SD) scenario and the double-degenerate (DD) scenario. In the first one, a (C-O) white dwarf accretes hydrogen- or helium-rich material from a non-degenerate companion (Whelan & Iben 1973) until it approaches the Chandrasekhar mass, $M_{Ch} = 1.4M_{\odot}$, contracts and explodes (Chandrasekhar 1931). In the SD scenario when the white dwarf is reaching the Chandrasekhar limit mass, the material inside contracts to the center. At the same time, and because of this contraction, the temperature starts to rise and rapid thermonuclear reactions take place fusing C and O to iron-group elements. Finally, once the thermonuclear energy generation rate exceeds the neutrino losses a nuclear flame forms and the supernova takes place, Hoyle & Fowler (1960).

In the double-degenerate scenario, two (C-O) white dwarfs with masses lower than M_{Ch} orbit each other and then merge by the emission of gravitational radiation (Webbink 1984). Particularly, if the masses of the two white dwarfs are different, the smaller one will be accreted onto the other. Due to conversion of the accreting (C-O) white dwarf into an (O-Ne-Mg) one, the star may collapse to a neutron star rather than exploding as a SNe Ia, as calculations by Nomoto & Iben (1985) have shown. A more interesting case concerning the DD scenario for SNe Ia is the one involving two WDs with approximately equal masses known as "violent merger", ending in a detonation (Pakmor et al. 2013).

As well as the possible progenitor scenarios another important aspect that is not totally understood is the flame propagation. There are two different modes of thermonuclear burning which both are hydrodynamically unstable to spatial perturbations (Hillebrandt & Niemeyer 2000): detonations, characterized by a strong shock wave and supersonic propagation and deflagrations, characterized by heat conduction, turbulence,

and subsonic propagation (Landau & Lifshitz 1959).

In a pure detonation M_{Ch} model, (Arnett 1969) the supersonic wave propagates very fast through the stellar matter before the white dwarf expands and the ejecta are composed mainly of nickel due to the fact that the material burns at high densities. In contrast, in a pure deflagration model (Nomoto et al. 1984) the subsonic wave is unable to surpass the expansion of the white dwarf and then also less heavy nuclei are formed, in agreement with what is observed (see Fig. 1.2). Further information about other possible scenarios, such as the delayed-detonation one, can be found in Khokhlov (1991); Mazzali et al. (2007).

However, according to observations of SNe Ia, and predicted synthetic observables of these different modes and sub-modes and there is no unique and valid theoretical SNe Ia description. All the burning processes could be in principle realized in nature, except for the pure detonation mode.

In the following chapter, we explain the basic concepts of "backwards modelling" and describe the basic aspects of the abundance tomography method to infer information about exploding star from spectral modelling. In Chapter 3, we describe the theory of radiative transfer and the Monte Carlo method focusing on TARDIS, the Monte Carlo Radiative Transfer code, used for this purpose. In the end, some conclusions are presented in Chapter 4.

2 Objectives

As we explained in the previous chapter, SNe Ia play a crucial role in the determination of cosmic distances and can be calibrated as standard candles. In general terms, SNe Ia are believed to be thermonuclear explosions of white dwarfs in which Carbon and Oxygen are fused to Fe-group elements, predominantly to ^{56}Ni . There are still uncertainties concerning their progenitors and the explosion mechanism, spectra, being a fundamental aspect, include different information about the progenitor system and they are the link between theoretical explosion models and observations (Stehle et al. 2005).

Theoretical approaches to model explosions of SNe Ia can be divided into two classes: "forward modelling" and "backward modelling". The first one, "forward modelling", consist of simulating a particular scenario from the beginning. It computes a theoretical model of ignition and ejecta evolution by means of hydrodynamic simulations and a detailed description of the burning processes, like in Reinecke et al. (2002) for the SD models. Finally, one obtains a model with few free parameters which may or may not reproduce certain observed data, but this approach is complex, needs a lot of time to operate and is computational expensive, making "forward modelling" unsuitable for extensive parameter studies.

The second theoretical approach is "backward modelling". As the name suggests we start with an inverse approach by analysing observations and try to fit them by means of a model using basic numerical techniques. This is done for grids of parameters in order to single out a group of parameters that fit the observed data well. This approach is characterized by a decrease of computational costs as an advantage, but it leads to a set of many parameters which strongly depend on assumptions. Nevertheless, they may provide useful information that complement "forward modelling" and improve our

understanding about SNe Ia (Stehle et al. 2005; Mazzali et al. 2007; Hachinger et al. 2009; Kerzendorf & Sim 2014).

An example of "backward modelling" is the Abundance Tomography method (ATM). It can be applied to SNe Ia and was first introduced by Stehle et al. (2005) for this purpose. This method makes use of a radiative transfer code and fits spectral time series to obtain the abundance stratification of the ejecta with density profile, velocity, temperature and abundances as the input parameters. As time runs, the ejecta evolve and we are able to observe deeper layers of ejecta contributing to the formation of the spectra. As more previously unseen layers become visible we are able to obtain the composition of every shell by fitting the location of the photosphere, obtained from the velocity of the absorption lines close to the inner boundary, in the time series and finally perform a tomography of the observed ejecta.

The main objective of this Bachelor Thesis is the understanding of the "backwards modelling" concept using the Abundance Tomography Method described in the last paragraphs of this section, by terms of the Monte Carlo Radiative Transfer code TARDIS (Kerzendorf & Sim 2014). First we will introduce the radiative transfer concept, addressing it properly for the different Monte Carlo methods and next we confirm the validity of the mentioned code, TARDIS.

3 Methodology

3.1 Radiative Transfer

For most objects in astrophysics electromagnetic radiation is the best tool for obtaining information about the objects under study. Radiative Transfer (RT) describes how radiation energy is emitted, absorbed and transported through matter, understanding then the high importance of RT calculations in astrophysics.

The radiation field is characterized by the *specific intensity*,

$$I_\nu = I(\mathbf{x}, t; \mathbf{n}, \nu) \equiv \frac{d\varepsilon}{dA \cos \theta d\Omega d\nu dt} \quad (3.1.1)$$

that represents, in a time interval dt and at every location \mathbf{x} , the energy $d\varepsilon$ transported by radiation in a frequency range $[\nu, \nu + d\nu]$ across an area dA into a solid angle $d\Omega$ along the propagation direction \mathbf{n} , where θ represents the angle between the propagation direction and the normal of the surface element. All these details and more information can be found in Mihalas (1978) or Mihalas & Mihalas (1984).

In major part the features appearing in the spectral energy distribution of the radiation field are due to the interaction of matter and radiation. The specific intensity I_ν is not constant. The changes are due to absorption and emission processes that remove or add energy, respectively. The RT equation describes all these events along a ray through a medium. In spherical symmetry (Mihalas & Mihalas 1984), an approximation that is adopted by TARDIS, the RT equation is:

$$\frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} I_\nu + \mu \frac{\partial I_\nu}{\partial r} + \frac{1 - \mu^2}{r} \frac{\partial I_\nu}{\partial \mu} = \eta_\nu - \kappa_\nu I_\nu \quad (3.1.2)$$

where c is the speed of light, μ is the cosine of the emission angle and r denotes the radius.

In the RT equation, the emissivity η_ν addresses the rate at which energy is added to the radiation field. Another important quantity, describing the energy removal from the ray, is the opacity χ_ν .

To determine all these interaction processes we can use the co-moving frame (CMF), where the matter is at rest. Due to the angle-independence of the material functions of many interaction processes the CMF is best suited for the description of radiation matter interactions. In contrast the Laboratory rest frame (LF) where time intervals and distances are best determined is optimal for describing the packet propagation. The frequency changes while changing between the frame due to the Doppler effect. To first order in $\frac{v}{c}$ the frequency in the CMF is given by:

$$\nu' = D_\mu \nu, \quad (3.1.3)$$

where D_μ represents the first order Doppler factor

$$D_\mu = 1 - \frac{\mu v}{c}. \quad (3.1.4)$$

Here v denotes the velocity and ν is the respective LF frequency.

Finally, we introduce two basic aspects that determine the efficiency of the different interaction processes; the *mean free path* of radiation, the average distance a photon moves without interacting with matter, and the *optical depth*, the average number of interactions of a photon along a path element. These two quantities are given, respectively, by:

$$\lambda_\nu = \frac{1}{\chi_\nu}, \quad (3.1.5)$$

$$d\tau = \chi ds \quad (3.1.6)$$

with ds as the path element.

RT as discussed in this section is hard to solve due to non local coupling and due to the dependence of opacity and emissivity on the radiation field. In order to solve this complex system, iterations and numerical approaches are needed. In the next section we will describe the radiation transport for the case of supernovae ejecta focusing on Monte Carlo Radiative Transfer methods and the code TARDIS.

3.2 Monte Carlo Radiative Transfer Methods and TARDIS

The Monte Carlo Radiative Transfer (MCRT) method tracks the propagation of many representative photons to be able to solve for the evolution of the radiation field. The Monte Carlo (MC) method is a probabilistic approach. It can be applied to arbitrary geometries and is useful due to the possible application to complex physical interactions like scattering processes, among others. The biggest disadvantage of this method involves statistical variations, and to overcome this problem large number of packets have to be used. As a result MC methods require large computational resources. However, the availability of these resources is constantly increasing, making the MCRT approach computationally feasible. One can find a wide use of MC methods in: Lucy (2005); Kasen et al. (2006); Kromer & Sim (2009) for supernovae, Abbott & Lucy (1985); Lucy & Abbott (1993); Vink et al. (2000) in hot-star winds and Long & Knigge (2002); Noebauer et al. (2010); Higginbottom et al. (2013) for disk winds.

3.2.1 Random Sampling

For the simulation of the different physical processes, in all MC methods a series of random number experiments is needed. We can use random number generators, that create uniformly distributed values. The physical processes can be described by probability distribution functions for example the probability that a packet travels an *optical depth* before being absorbed is $e^{-\tau_\nu}$. We then map them onto the uniformly and available set of random numbers. The inverse transformation method is used to define the mapping, provided by the calculation of the cumulative distribution functions of two ran-

dom variables, associating both variables and inverting the final result. The complete mathematical derivation of the inverse transformation method is described in Kalos & Whitlock (2008).

3.2.2 The Radiative Transfer code TARDIS

In our Bachelor thesis we present the RT code TARDIS, an open-source, one-dimensional spherically symmetric and time independent code used for rapid spectral modelling of supernovae which uses MC methods to obtain a self-consistent description of the plasma state and to compute a synthetic spectrum. It is written in Python and C and was introduced by Kerzendorf & Sim (2014). More information about the code can be found at <http://tardis.rtfld.org> and can be obtained for free at <https://github.com/tardis-sn/tardis.git>.

3.2.3 Discretization and Initialization

At the beginning of every MC radiative transfer cycle the radiation field at the inner boundary is discretized into a collection of indivisible energy packets. The modelling of the inner boundary follows the Schuster-Schwarzschild approximation (Mazzali & Lucy 1993), where the continuum radiation is created in an inner region below the photosphere with a black-body frequency distribution. The photospheric luminosity is given by

$$L_{\text{BB}} = 4\pi R_{\text{ph}}^2 \sigma T_{\text{eff}}^4, \quad (3.2.1)$$

where R_{ph} is the radius of the photosphere, σ is the Stefan-Boltzmann constant and T_{eff} is the effective temperature.

The CMF frequencies of the packets are sampled from the Planck function for the given temperature T_{eff} (Lucy 1999). Another important aspect to consider is the initial direction of the MC packets, given by the cosine of the emission angle μ . Using the inverse transformation method:

$$\mu = \sqrt{z}, \quad (3.2.2)$$

where z is a uniformly distributed random number between $[0,1]$.

Once the initialization stage is finished, the energy packets propagate in the LF across the ejecta. We will proceed by tracking propagation of these packets to see any possible change in the direction or frequency, and finally determine if they end up leaving the computational domain of the ejecta or scatter back into the photosphere. Finally, by studying the probabilistic information obtained from every single MC packet, we are able to reconstruct the evolution of the radiation field and determine the synthetic spectrum.

3.2.4 Monte Carlo packet propagation

As we introduced in the previous subsections, the tracking of interactions and in which process they undergo for every MC packet it is highly important to be able to solve and determine the different properties of the RT. To achieve a proper tracking and characterize the radiation-matter interactions, we need to determine the optical depth, presented in (3.1.6), along the packet path, but not without first knowing the detailed plasma conditions of the ejecta, more specifically the ionization and excitation states, that will determine the opacity and the emissivity.

The properties of the supernova ejecta vary with atomic processes like electron scattering, free-free, bound-bound (BB) and bound-free transitions (Kromer & Sim 2009). The packets simulate using TARDIS the same interaction processes that real photons can encounter.

Two important opacities in the SNe Ia ejecta are included in the code TARDIS: Thomson scattering treated as a coherent process where the propagation direction of the photons vary but not their energy and frequency in the CMF and BB transitions evaluated by TARDIS in the Sobolev approximation (Sobolev 1960). We refer to Kerzendorf & Sim (2014) for more information about the different available excitation processes.

In TARDIS, three different processes are able to stop the trajectory of a packet: crossing the boundary of a shell, Thomson scattering or absorption by a BB transition. These processes are directly related with some specific distances that are determined as: d_S , the distance to the next shell boundary along the packet trajectory, d_T refers to the

distance to the next Thomson scattering and d_L , the distance a packet needs to cover to Doppler shift into resonance with the next line transition. More information can be found in Kerzendorf & Sim (2014)

If d_L is the shortest distance the packet may experience a BB transition, otherwise if the shortest distance is d_T , the next interaction is a Thomson scattering. Finally if d_S is the shortest distance the packet propagation continues in the next shell where d_L , d_T and d_S are determined again.

3.2.5 Spectral Synthesis

In order to determine the synthetic spectrum packet properties are stored when a packet reaches the outer boundary. The recorded packets are binned in frequency to obtain the synthetic spectrum. As we introduced in the beginning of this section, the main problem for MC calculations is the presence of MC noise. To address this issue TARDIS uses an algorithm similar to the one used in Sim (2004) that improves the signal to noise of the resulting spectra.

The key ingredient in this algorithm is the introduction of *virtual* (v -) packets that have the same properties as the *real* packets but vary in the direction of propagation and the CMF energy. To get a better estimate of the emergent spectrum a collection of v -packets is created each time a *real* packet has a change of their assigned trajectory due to interactions.

Another important aspect about these v -packets is that there is not a change in their direction due to the lack of interaction with matter but instead, only the total optical depth τ_ν is recorded. Finally, the contribution of a v -packet to the synthetic spectrum in the frequency range $[\nu, \nu + d\nu]$ is given by

$$L_\nu = \frac{\epsilon_\nu}{\Delta t \Delta \nu} e^{-\tau_\nu}, \quad (3.2.3)$$

where Δt is the time interval represented by the simulation, ϵ_ν is the energy and $e^{-\tau_\nu}$ is the probability that a packet covers an optical depth τ_ν without any interaction.

3.3 Application of TARDIS

3.3.1 Running TARDIS

To solve RT calculations an atomic dataset is required for the calculation of the ionization/excitation state of the plasma, radiative rate coefficients and bound-bound opacities among others (Kerzendorf & Sim 2014). This atomic database is based on the line list by Kurucz & Bell (1995); Dere et al. (1997).

The input parameters when using TARDIS are the time since explosion t_{exp} , the density profile, the chemical composition, the emergent luminosity L_e and the velocity boundaries of the computational grid. The atmosphere is confined between an inner and an outer boundary and is divided into multiple cells. The ejecta of this model is defined in a custom velocity grid, where the packets will propagate and may interact with matter via Thomson scattering or BB transitions, as explained previously. At the end of the propagation and from the escaping packets synthetic spectra can be obtained.

In the next subsection, we will present a simple TARDIS computation and discuss the resulting synthetic spectrum.

3.3.2 Example TARDIS Calculation

In Figure 3.1 we present a synthetic spectrum obtained using TARDIS. The input parameters are; for the requested luminosity of $9.44 \log_{10}(L_o/L_\odot) \text{ ergs}^{-1}$, a time since explosion t_{exp} of 13 days and a simple power-law density profile corresponding to a seventh order fit to the Nomoto et al. (1984) W7 model.

In the figure, we can observe some important spectral features. We can see a Ca II line at $\sim 3750 \text{ \AA}$, a weak Si II line $\sim 4000 \text{ \AA}$, the Mg II line around $\sim 4250 \text{ \AA}$ and a strong Si II line around $\sim 6150 \text{ \AA}$. It is important to mention that this is not a good model, it represents a very simple model where iron group elements are not taken into account which, however, are important in more accurate models.

Figure 3.1: Synthetic spectrum of a customized TARDIS simulation.

3.3.3 Backwards Modelling with TARDIS

We start with different assumptions on the composition and the density and we compare with the observed data in order to adjust the model. From the early spectra we fit the outer shells and as the photosphere recedes more shells become transparent. The ATM accounts for the outer shells as more layers are fitted. With this ATM people analyzed a lot of different SN like in Hachinger et al. (2009).

In Figure 3.2 one can see a typical abundance stratification profile of a supernova of Type Iax (SNe Iax): fast decaying and faint supernovae with SN 2002cx as the prototype of this class. The main observational properties are low expansion velocities, lack of high-velocity features in early-time spectra and the appearance of Fe II lines near-maximum.

The results of the abundance tomography, performed in Figure 3.2 shows a dominance of cobalt and iron below $\sim 10000 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, oxygen and cobalt dominating above $\sim 10000 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, with cobalt disappearing at $\sim 12000 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ and oxygen becoming the most abundant chemical element at $\sim 12000 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. This is comparable to most SNe Iax characterised by an abundance profile separated into two different regimes: a well-mixed region under 10000 km s^{-1} and a stratified region with decreasing IGE abundances above

Figure 3.2: The stratified abundance profile from the TARDIS fitting process of SN 2011ay spectra, a SN Iax (taken from Barna et al. (2017)). The vertical axis represents the mass fraction of the different abundances. The horizontal axis represents the velocity in homologous expansion, where the velocity is proportional to the radius of a specific layer. Low velocities represent inner layers and high velocities represent outer layers of the ejecta.

10 000 $km s^{-1}$. All different properties and further information about SNe Iax and the different applicabilities of TARDIS can be found in Barna et al. (2017).

4 Conclusion and Outlook

Type Ia Supernovae are of great importance as cosmic distance indicators. However many details of the explosion remain unknown. One possible way to get more insights about the physical properties of the explosion is "backwards modelling" where we use RT to infer information from the observations. For that purpose we can use the fast, flexible and open source MC code TARDIS (Kerzendorf & Sim 2014), which we have examined in detail in this work.

This code is used for the abundance tomography method in order to obtain the stratification of the ejecta. One can be able to use TARDIS changing the different input parameters to obtain different synthetic spectra in order to visualize how it fits in the observed information. We can get a closer insight about how useful information is obtained using TARDIS in Barna et al. (2017)

In all abundance tomography approaches it is used a very restricted density profile, usually the W7 model. Exceptions exist but models far from the M_{Ch} ones have not been analysed yet. A possible study in order to figure out which are the properties of the progenitor system and the chemical evolution involves TARDIS calculations of different density profiles. In the near future, one can do that and also obtain useful information of the density distribution in the star.

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